

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COOPERATION IN ADJUSTMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN TO SCHOOL

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Abstract: This article talks about continuity between preschool and school as a condition for successful adaptation of children to school.

Key words: continuity, preschool education, primary education, state requirements, school preparation.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev states that "*modern preschool education plays an important role in raising a healthy and mature generation.*"

Currently, special attention is paid to preparing children for high-quality school education in preschool educational organizations under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a proof of this, in 2018, the coverage of children in preschool education was 34.4%, and at the end of the half-year of 2019, this indicator was 40.5%.

This is definitely the result of the decisions and attention of the head of state in the field of preschool education. A valid question arises here. How to turn the educational process from a difficult one into a joyful one? It is worth mentioning that quality education depends primarily on the professional skills of the educator and pedagogue.

Of course, the inclusion of innovations in training, the use of advanced work methods and methods will lead to an increase in the quality of education. This, in turn, requires professional skills from the pedagogue. We all know that the first and most perfect educator for a child is a parent. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issues of cooperation with the family, especially the importance of the role of fathers in raising children.

In the years of independence, the country adopted the "Law on Education" and "National Personnel Training Program" regulating the activities of educational institutions. Great changes have taken place in the field of education, including preschool education, which is the first level of education.

Article 30 of the "Law on Education" increased the role and responsibility of parents in the upbringing of children and their education, protection of their legal rights and interests. The transition of a preschool-age child to school education brought about serious radical changes in his life, morals, interests and relationships.

Modern pedagogy requires unique innovations in teaching, educating and developing each student, and often traditional methods overlap with non-traditional methods. Currently, in understanding the child's readiness for school, there has been a shift of attention from intellectual readiness to personal readiness, which is determined by the formed "internal position of the student". In the first place are formed cognitive motives of learning, that is, the

child's conscious desire to learn new things based on already acquired knowledge. Thus, for a modern 1st grader, it is not important to have a cognitive tool, but to use it consciously.

State requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan are determined by the following areas of child development:

- physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle;
- socio-emotional development;
- speech, communication, reading and writing skills;
- development of the cognitive process;
- creative development.

One of the most urgent problems of the modern educational process is the problem of continuity. The issue of implementation of continuity is considered every year in a new way, in the process of introducing new methods and methods of teaching.

The main tasks of cooperation between the preschool educational organization and the school are as follows:

- establishing a unity of views on the educational process between the kindergarten, family and school;
- development of common goals and educational tasks, ways to achieve the intended results;
- creating conditions for comfortable interaction of all participants of the educational process - pedagogues, teachers, children and parents;
- all-round psychological and pedagogical training of parents;
- providing psychological support in understanding one's family and social resources, contributing to solving problems when the child enters school.

The most important condition for the effectiveness of work on establishing continuity between kindergarten and school is a clear understanding of the goals, tasks and content of the implementation of continuity.

At the same time, continuity in primary education is implemented in several directions, that is, mutual cooperation of teachers and educators, mutual visits of teachers and educators to open classes, analysis of children's adaptation at the beginning of the school year and their success at the end of the year, children of the preparatory group and elementary school students. joint training with, work with parents of future 1st graders and so on. The relationship between parents and a school psychologist helps to develop criteria for children's readiness for school education. Adjusting to school in 1st grade is a difficult test for many children. The child faces a number of problems that he cannot solve on his own, and as a result, mental stress may develop. Early diagnosis is carried out in September together with teachers, psychologists, parents to determine and adapt the initial development level of the educational and educational process, taking into account the individual characteristics of children, and in April - the level of education is determined, based on this, parents and children recommendations are developed for

How to ensure children's high potential and success when they go to school? First of all, in the process of preparing for school, it is necessary to change the target direction of educational activities. At this stage of the formation of the child's thinking, instead of meaningful components, developmental components should prevail. The services of the designers and pedagogues of the preschool educational institution should be aimed at

directing each child to activities, analyzing the characteristics of objects and events, that is, distributing objects according to the indicated signs, distinguishing their differences and general characteristics. must

Thus, even before the beginning of the school year, the teacher has a sufficiently complete understanding of the children, their abilities, what competencies they acquired in kindergarten, their health, family, living conditions, and the environment of each child.

In order to increase the interest of preschool children in studying at school, excursions are organized throughout the year: to the school grounds, to the school library, to the gym and, of course, to the future classroom.

By organizing various events, children make friends with each other, communicate, share impressions, because the 1st graders are their classmates from yesterday's kindergarten. This makes it easier for them to get used to school life at the beginning of their studies. They are related to the socio-economic processes taking place in our society. It is also related to the constantly growing flow of information, changing living conditions and the emergence of new requirements for people.

Coordinated, friendly work preparation team of school and kindergarten allows to assess the adaptation of graduates, talk about each child, try to help him based on the observations made on him.

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